

Language Choice Used by Balinese Young Generation in Sanur Beach

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ABSTRACT : This research is about sociolinguistics which focuses on choosing the language used by the young Balinese generation on the Sanur beach. This research used Joshua Fishman's theory. The purpose of this study was to identify the choice of Balinese language for the young generation in Sanur, the factors that influence the choice of the use of Balinese in the young generation, the importance of language use, the choice of language according to the young Balinese generation, and the obstacles of the young Balinese generation in using the language. The researcher used a qualitative descriptive approach to manage the data selection in this study. The data is taken from the questionnaire results given by the researcher as the instrument of this research. The data collection results show that the language chosen by the young Balinese generation in Sanur beach is Indonesian. The overall results of this study show that the language choice of the young Balinese generation influenced the language recipient factor and the level of importance of the language itself.

KEYWORDS - Young Generation, Language Choice, Sociolinguistics

I. INTRODUCTION

There are many discussions about the relationship between language and society. Language cannot be separated from the society wherein it is spoken. Language and society are correlated with the effort to explain what language is used in a certain society or, in this case, in a multilingual society, why people speak differently in different social contexts. Wardhaugh (2010) stated that society is any group of people drawn together for a certain purpose or purpose. Every communication or interaction that happens in society usually involves a variety of languages.

One of the linguistics branches that have many cases to be analyzed is sociolinguistics. Sociolinguistics is the study of the social uses of language and the most productive studies in the four decades of sociolinguistic research that have emanated from determining the social evaluation of linguistic variants. In sociolinguistics, the term domain cannot be separated from bilingualism and diglossia because of the obligation to choose the right language or variety of languages by the sociocultural norms in the speech community concerned. In a bilingual society, each language is associated with different areas of use. Fishman (1972) proposed this concept to explain language use behaviour in a bilingual society and, at the same time to see patterns of shift and maintenance of language in that society. In communicating with all people, they need a language because language is one of the most important things for humans (Oktira et al., 2022). In sociolinguistics, examining the way how the language is used in different social contexts is considered a useful way to determine not only the way language works but also the social relationships in a particular society, as well as the way how people set up and express their social identity through the use of language (Holmes & Wilson, 2017). In terms of the position and function of language in society, the use and choice of language are essentially related to the status of a language in society, which can refer to the concept of diglossia (Ferguson, 1959). This concept states that each language or variety of languages, whether in monolingual, bilingual, or multilingual communities, has a different role and function according to its designation.

Hickerson (2000) stated that sociolinguistics is a study of linguistic development that makes language variations the focus, then looks at language variations based on their social context. Hudson (1996) stated that Sociolinguistics is the term between society and language, sociolinguistics, the study of language and society to find out the branch of knowledge of people which studies the social aspects of language is. Sociolinguistics concentrates on the interrelationships between social factors and language variations. Fishman (1972) stated that sociolinguistics is a study of the characteristics of language variation, the characteristics of the function of language use with the characteristics of the language users. The third one is always interacting change and changing each other in a speech community. Soeparno (2002) defines that "Sociolinguistics is a science which studies language variation by relating it to variables outside language itself, such as social, economic status, geographical origin, age, social distance, setting.

Both linguistic and external factors influence language choice as a social phenomenon. Language choice is closely related to the situation of the speaker's social community. For example, the difference in age and level of education can affect people's language choices in their communication with others. Other than that, the situation in which the conversation happens also affects how a language will be used.

According to Fasold (2008), a language choice is a person in a bilingual or multilingual community speaking two or more languages and having to choose which language to use (Fasold, 2008). Language choice may be influenced by factors related to some individuals or speakers in need, their associations, or aspects of the social situation. Certain choices can be influenced by several variables, perhaps from different weights. Language choice is the choice of words, phrases, clauses or other language sentences in the speaker's linguistic repertoire. For bilingual and multilingual, the emergence of language choices seems natural, automatic and unplanned. The emergence of language selection is caused by the occurrence of language, social, and cultural contact so that a growing group of speech communities can choose a language or language code in a particular event, either maintaining the first language or shifting language to a new language or mixing first language and new language. The choice of language makes us use the language all the time. Our language choice can also be a reflection of the social group we associate with certain words or types of linguistic behaviour.

Suharyo (2018) stated that defence language and language shift are like two sides of one coin that cannot be separated. The second is the collective result of language selection. Meanwhile, important factors in maintaining a language are the existence, concern for future generations, belief, and loyalty of the supporting community. The choice of language should be applied when we want to talk to each other. With our chosen language, consciousness can speak more politely in conversation. As a good society, language selection must be applied in every conversation. The awareness of choice of language supports us to give a good presentation and improve competence and performance in our environment. In other words, someone who chooses the language in his communication is applying his communicative competence or is showing his communicative performance. As a behaviour, the choice of language is essentially an action or behaviour in using a selected language based on the available situation.

However, for this study, the term 'language selection' refers to communicative performance or language behaviour (language behaviour) even though language behaviour contains a broader understanding. One of the social interactions of people with language diversity clearly explains that today's children always create a new image of themselves even though it violates many existing norms (Duha et al., 2022). Do not use language. Make what they use that combines letters with numbers, lengthen or shorten the use of letters or vary upper and lower case letters to form words and sentences.

Language also plays an important role for the younger generation (Angraini & Yulis, 2019). Some cases happen in society about language attitude. One of them is found in Balinese people that stay in Sanur Beach. For example, they use a language when they do not talk with others in their place. Speaking language choice in polite language is needed to make others accept the statements well and make it a language characteristic of them. So, the role of language choice is important to know to send a message of communication. With direct communication which happens, make Balinese people that stay in Sanur Beach become able to determine the language that should be applied.

In sociolinguistics, the term domain cannot be separated from bilingualism and diglossia because of the obligation to choose the right language or variety of languages by the sociocultural norms in the speech community concerned. In a bilingual society, each language is associated with different areas of use. Fishman (1972) proposed this concept to explain language use behaviour in a bilingual society and, at the same time to see patterns of shift and maintenance of language in that society. Based on the concept of the realm, from several languages in one's language repertoire, it can be seen that the language is always used in intragroup interactions and is used for interaction between groups (Siregar et al., 1998). To see the choice and the use of language in speakers, domain theory is needed. The domain is a term created by Joshua Fishman. He defines a domain as an abstract illustration of sociocultural communication topics, relations between communicators, and where the communication takes place according to the social structure of the speakers. Certain social factors, speakers, social context of the conversation, functions and topics of the conversation are important in consideration of language choice in different speakers (Fishman, 1972). The concept of domain is used to describe language-used behaviour. The domains are defined as institutional contexts in the use of language (Fishman, 1972). The concept of domain developed by Fishman 1971, the domain is a sociocultural construct abstracted from topics of communication, relationships between communicators, and locales of communication, in accord with the institutions of a society and the spheres of activity of a speech community.

Fishman (1972) mentions four domains, family, neighbourhood, work, and religion. (Parasher, 1991) used seven domains in his research language choice among educated people in the southern part of India: the domain is family, friendship, neighbourhood, transactions, education, government and employment. Meanwhile, Greenfield in Sumarsono (1990) used only five domains in his research on Puerto Rico in New York City, namely family, kinship, religion, education, and work. The concept domain that he used is Fishman's 1968 point of view. If the speaker as the buyer speaks in the market with the participant as a seller on a topic, the speaker is said in the transaction domain. The observed domain argues that domain is a theoretical concept that marks an interaction situation based on the same experience and is bound to make the same goals and obligations, such as family, neighbourhood, religion, and occupation.

In this research, the researcher is interested in observing the phenomenon of language choice by the young Balinese generation in Sanur beach based on the sociolinguistic paradigm. Why researcher is interested in this research because Sanur Beach is one of the famous tourist destinations in Bali. Sanur Tourism area is located in South Denpasar District. The increasing number of local, domestic and foreign visitors has made a lot of interaction, both oral and written, with the choice of the language of the community, especially the young generation. The language used by the young generation is usually influenced by interactions with tourists and social media that the young generation must access.

The young generation aged 17 to 30 years who are used as respondents are students and those who work related to tourism and live in international tourist destinations in Bali. in Sanur (Denpasar City). They were chosen as respondents because the young generation is very vulnerable to change and is very dynamic. Respondents to find out their choice of language for their mother tongue in communication because the higher the choice of Balinese language, they not only maintain the Balinese language but also increase expectations for the Balinese language by passing it on to the next level in life or their children later in life.

According to the background, the objectives of this research are to identify the language choice of the Balinese's young generation in Sanur. These factors influence the choice of the use of Balinese in the younger generation, the importance of the use of language choice according to the younger generation, and the obstacles of the young generation in using the Balinese language.

II. METHOD

This research used qualitative research using a descriptive approach. Creswell (2014) stated that qualitative research is a method of exploration and understanding the meaning. The qualitative method aims to explain phenomena by collecting and analyzing data. It means that qualitative research is a research design that describes factual phenomena.

Every research needed some steps that were usually called processes. Then, based on the statement of the problems and the significance of the research, the researcher would use descriptive qualitative research as the primary tool in this research to answer the statement of problems. This kind of research approach involves descriptive data collection as the basis for interpretation in the attempt to describe and interpret the phenomena of language choice used by Bali's generation.

The research will be conducted by giving questionnaires to the objects/ samples. This method is used to find language choice and the factors of the Balinese People that stay in Sanur beach for choosing a particular language to communicate with others. The multilingual speaker needs to make the right language choices in a multilingual community. This research investigates factors that govern language choices multilingual speakers make in the Balinese people in Sanur Beach.

In this research, eight domains or classifications of language use are examined: They were characteristics of respondents, the young generation's language skills, the generation's language acquisition, the young generation's choice of languages, choice of use of Balinese in the young generation, factors affecting the choice of the use of Balinese in the young generation, the level of interest in using language choices according to the young generation, barriers to the young generation using Balinese. From the data, give questionnaire on language use, and participant observations are employed. The paper notes that due to changes in various spheres of life in Sanur Beach. The observations were conducted in Sanur Beach. The focus is on the Balinese people in Sanur Beach. The researcher would like to see their language options when they talk to people around them. The researcher will provide questionnaires to them and analyze the factors by choosing what language Bali is.

The data in this research is the respondents' answers obtained from the filled questionnaire. Samples from this research were taken from as many as 30 people. To do this research, the researcher needs data sources. The data source in this study is the result of a questionnaire from the Bali's Generation in Sanur Beach.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the researcher finds the language choices of the younger generation of Balinese on the Sanur beach and tries to describe them based on classification.

3.1 Characteristics of Respondents

Respondents in this study were divided into three characteristics, namely age, gender, and origin of the respondent. Each characteristic of the respondents is described as follows.

a. characteristics of respondents by age

Tabel 1. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

Respondent's age	Frequency
17-20	12
21-25	11
26-30	7

Based on table 1. Characteristics of respondents based on age, it is explained that there are three types of age classification based on the age range, namely 17 until 20 years old with a frequency of 12 people, age 21 until 25 years old with a frequency of 11 and age 26 until 30 years old with 7 people respondent. It can be seen that the age of 17 until 20 years is the most age who participated as respondents, and the age of 26 until 30 years is the age of the respondents who are few.

b. Characteristics of respondents by gender

Tabel 2. Characteristics of respondents by gender

Gender	Frequency
Male	14
Female	16

It can be seen from the table above that there are two genders used in this study. The gender consists of male and female. Both sexes have the amount obtained by researchers when collecting data on the Sanur beach. The number of male respondents consisted of 14 people and the number of women consisted of 16 people. The number of respondents based on gender between men and women is 30 people.

c. Characteristics based on respondents from the region

Tabel 3. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Regional Origin

Origin of Respondent	Frequency
Sanur	30

The table above is an explanation of the research locations that have been carried out by researchers on the Sanur beach, Bali. The researcher found that there were respondents who were born and lived in Bali who specifically understood the Balinese language itself. And there are several respondents born and living in Bali who can't speak Balinese

1. Young Generation's Language Skills

Tabel 4. Young Generation's Language Skills

Language Skill	Frequency
Balinese	3
Indonesian	2
English	-
Balinese and Indonesian	14
Indonesian and English	-
Balinese, Indonesian and English	11

Based on table 4. The language skills of the Balinese young generation explains that the young generation preferred to language skills in Balinese and Indonesian with a total of 14 people.

3.2 Generation Language Acquisition

Tabel 5. Young Generation Language Acquisition

language Acquisition	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
School	8	21	16
Family	23	12	-
Neighbour	13	5	1
Work environment	2	8	4

The table above shows the language acquisition obtained Balinese young generation which is divided into three parts, the different types of language used are many that appear, namely; Balinese, Indonesian and English.

Researchers have divided four parts of the domain used, namely; school, family, neighbors, and work environment. The most common Balinese language acquisition is 23 people and in the work environment two people acquire the language. In the school environment, Indonesian is the language most widely used by the

young generation and the neighboring environment is rarely used. English is obtained in schools with a frequency of 16 people and in families the acquisition of English is not obtained by the young generation of Bali based on respondents' statements.

3.3 Young Generation's Choice of Languages

Based on the results of data analysis, it was found that Balinese, Indonesian, especially English are used by the young generation at beaches, schools, homes, temples, markets, work environments, and neighbors.

a. Young Generation's Choice of Languages and Their Use on the Beach

Language Usage	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
Beaches	8	17	-

Based on the table above, it is explained that the use of Indonesian on the beach with a frequency of 17 people, thus Indonesian language is often used on the beach.

b. Young Generation's Choice of Languages and Their Use in Schools

Language Usage	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
Schools	8	25	20

Based on the table above, it is explained that the use of Indonesian in schools is with a frequency of 25 people, thus Indonesian is often used on the beach. As many as 20 people use English, thus Balinese at least in schools as an intermediary to communicate.

c. The choice of the language of the younger generation and its use at home

Language Usage	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
Homes	20	12	-

It can be seen above that the use of Balinese at home is often used by the young generation of Bali with a frequency of 20 people and English is not used as an intermediary to communicate in the home environment.

d. The choice of the language of the young generation and its use at the temple

Language Usage	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
Temple	15	10	-

The table above explains that Balinese is often used by young Balinese in temples with a frequency of 15 people and English is not used by temples as an intermediary for communication.

e. *The choice of the language of the younger generation and its use in the Market*

Language Usage	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
Markets	9	10	-

In the market, the young generation uses Indonesian and Balinese as intermediaries for transactions between sellers and buyers and English is not used by the young generation of Balinese based on the data collected by researchers.

f. *The choice of the language of the younger generation and its use in the Work Environment*

Language Usage	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
Work environment	3	15	-

It can be seen above that the use of Indonesian in the work environment is a language that is often used by the young generation of Bali with a frequency of 15 people and English is not used as an intermediary to communicate in the work environment.

g. *The choice of the language of the younger generation and its use in the Neighborhood*

Language Usage	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
Neighbour	7	14	-

Based on the table above, it is explained that the use of Indonesian in the neighboring environment with a frequency of 14 people, thus Indonesian is often used in the neighboring environment. As many as 7 people use Balinese language, thus English is not used in the environment as an intermediary to communicate based on the results of the researcher's survey on the respondent's statement.

3.5 Choice of the Use of Balinese in the Young Generation

a. *Choice of the Use of Balinese in the Young Generation*

Language Usage	Frequency
	Balinese
Beaches	8
Schools	8
Homes	20
Temple	15
Markets	9
Work environment	3
Neighbor	7

b. Choice of the Use of Indonesian in the Young Generation

Language Usage	Frequency
	Indonesian
Beaches	17
Schools	25
Homes	12
Temple	10
Markets	10
Work environment	15
Neighbor	14

c. Choice of the Use of English in the Young Generation

Language Usage	Frequency
	English
Beaches	-
Schools	20
Homes	-
Temples	-
Markets	-
Work environment	-
Neighbors	-

Based on the description table above, it is explained that English is used by the younger generation of Bali only in schools with a frequency of 20 people. Thus it can be concluded that English is only acquired and used in schools.

3.6 Factors Affecting the Choice of the Use of Balinese in the Young Generation

Reasons to use Balinese	Reasons for not using Balinese
Mother Tongue	It's hard to use smooth Balinese language
The dominant population knows and using Balinese	The interlocutor is not in Balinese
Understandable for balinese	

This section explains the reasons for using the Balinese language and the reasons for not using the Balinese . The younger generation of Bali states that Balinese is their mother tongue, Balinese knows and uses Balinese itself, and the last one is easy for Balinese to understand. The language has a language level, where there is a smooth language and there is a rough language (colloquial language), the younger generation is not able to speak Balinese smooth. apart from that most of the interlocutors can't speak Balinese.

3.7 The Level of Interest in Using Language Choices According to the Young Generation

Level of Interest	Frequency		
	Balinese	Indonesian	English
More Important	25	28	-
Important	5	3	5
Not too important	-	-	25
Not important	-	-	-

Based on the table above at number 7. The level of importance of language choice according to the younger generation of Bali explains that Indonesia as a language is more important than Balinese with a frequency of 28 people, and English is a language that is less important to communicate with a frequency of 25 people.

3.8 Barriers to the Young Generation Using Balinese

No	Barriers to using Balinese
1.	They do not know smooth Balinese
2.	Not all balinese can speak bali language
3.	language dominance is Indonesian

There are no barriers to the Balinese young generation in using the Balinese language, stating that the Balinese young generation cannot use the smooth Balinese. secondly, not all Balinese can speak Balinese, and the last is that Indonesian dominates as an intermediary language to communicate.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the result that the researcher divided it into domains. They were characteristics of respondents, the young generation's language skills, generation language acquisition, the young generation's choice of languages, choice of the use of Balinese in the young generation, factors affecting the choice of the use of Balinese in the young generation, the level of interest in using language choices according to the young generation, barriers to the young generation using Balinese.

Based on the discussion above, the young Balinese generation has different language choices according to where they are and to whom they are talking. However, Indonesian is the dominant language of all the dominants that researchers have identified. Moreover, English is the language least used by the young Balinese generation in Sanur to communicate. Indeed, there is a tendency that the young the respondent's age group seems, the greater the average choice of language. However, it only shows the frequency of interaction in various interactions, a common and natural phenomenon in a glossy society caused by socio-psychological factors between the speakers.

The young Balinese generation in Sanur can speak and use Balinese because Balinese is their mother tongue. In addition, Indonesian is a language often used to communicate in the coastal area, family, home, neighbours and the work environment. However, even though Sanur Beach is a tourist spot, the Balinese's young generation only sometimes uses English as an intermediary to communicate, even though some can speak English.

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